

Original Article

A Comparative Study of Perspectives of Academicians on Technological Noise in Online Education

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Abstract

This study demonstrates the impact of technological noise in online learning through comparative analysis of the perceptions of academicians at Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) Pakistan and Anadolu University (AU) Turkiye. "Technological noise" is interference from disruptive elements impeding smooth learning experiences. Both the universities have been pioneering open and distance learning in their respective countries; however, the presence of technological noise—in the form of hardware problems, software limitations, connectivity problems, and LMS inefficiencies—leads to significant disruptions to the pedagogical and learning processes. Employing a qualitative approach, the study used interviews to determine the technological disruptions faced by academicians at the two universities. Findings indicate that AU has a more effective technology management system, hence minimizing disruptions in the form of hardware, software, and connectivity, while AIOU experiences high levels of technological noise, which negatively impacts pedagogical effectiveness. In order to address the same, the study recommends institution-level interventions such as augmented technical support, enhanced network infrastructure, digital skill training, and optimized LMS functionality. The study also encourages collaborative pedagogy and knowledge-sharing programs between AIOU and AU such as cross-institutional workshops, mutual technical support networks, and faculty exchange programs. Through the integration of these interventions, both the universities may strengthen their online learning systems, reduce technological impediments, and enhance overall learning outcomes.

Keywords: Distance learning, online learning system, collaborative pedagogies, technology management system.

Introduction

In the past decade and ever more rapidly post COVID, distant education in Pakistan and Turkiye has experienced a significant shift towards online platforms. Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) and Anadolu University (AU) are leaders in the adoption of the technological leap. Both universities intend to ease the learning barrier in their countries. These two universities have expanded the scope of education to be inclusive and flexible towards their diverse students through new ways of teaching and technology. AIOU and Anadolu University, being leaders in open and distance learning, have assured that flexibility and availability in educational practices can facilitate the spread of knowledge and social development.

AIOU provides a range of online courses through its large-scale online learning management system, including virtual classrooms, multimedia content, and interactive content. The university employs e-books, online workshops, assignments, formative assessment, and discussion forums to facilitate students' learning across geographical borders. Anadolu University, Turkiye employs online media to present lectures, tests, and

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offer study material. The university has employed online resources to enhance student engagement and collaboration, developing a virtual learning environment that suits contemporary learners. Both institutions are dedicated to adopting technology to enhance education to be more accessible, flexible, and interactive, enabling students to attain their academic aspirations irrespective of location.

In their quest for the pledge towards technologically empowered distance education there is an intruding and disturbing element that infuses the smooth architecture of virtual classrooms. It is often referred to as "technological noise." This kind of technological noise frustrates the smooth course of education. It appears as all sorts of technical glitches, such as slow internet speed or inconsistency between user interfaces on different platforms, each performing its own role as a barrier to normal online learning activity. Noise produced through technology is an invasive force that exhorts to take into consideration its multifarious effects on the educational environment of online courses.

Comparison of the contextual aspects of online classes at AIOU and AU:

Table 1: Comparison of the context of Online Classes at AIOU and AU

Feature	Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU)	Anadolu University (AU)
Scheduling and Allocation	DRS collaborates with the ICT Department for scheduling workshops. Groups are allocated based on enrolment.	Distance Education Department in collaboration with the ICT team meticulously crafts the schedule at AU. Students in a course are grouped into a single virtual classroom.
Course Coordination	Coordinators receive schedule and login details. Special website is used to allocate resource persons for the courses. Resource persons are assigned by the course coordinators.	Coordinators at AU adhere to the course coordinator is responsible for teaching the course. Student allocation in a course is done by the moderators.
Learning Management System (LMS)	Workshops at AIOU run on aaghi.aiou.edu.pk. Three credit hours per online classes. Course, 2 hours session daily for a six-weekly, each lasting 45 minutes. Big day workshop. Microsoft teams is used for virtual classroom.	AU utilizes the e-kampus platform for online classes. Classes are structured weekly, each lasting 45 minutes. Big day workshop. Blue Button is used for virtual classroom.
Login Credentials	Resource persons at AIOU receive login credentials for aaghi and Teams. Identical credentials are used for convenience. The resource person joins virtual classroom by using the credentials.	Login details for coordinators and students at AU provided by the e-kampus virtual classroom by using the technical team. The moderator admits the resource person in the virtual classroom.
Presentation Upload and Sharing	Resource persons at AIOU deliver audio lectures where camera is not used. Audio recordings are available to the students after the session for the current semester. The resource persons develop and upload presentations for units. Share with students during live sessions through chat.	Coordinators at AU deliver video lectures where camera recording is done during the session which is available to the students for two semesters. The coordinators develop unit presentations and submit to the technical team (Moderators) for uploading during live sessions.
Attendance Monitoring	AIOU's system automatically marks student attendance upon login.	Attendance is not mandatory at AU, and it does not contribute to summative evaluation.

Feature	Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) Anadolu University (AU)
Evaluation Criteria	<p>Attendance not mandatory but influences grades.</p> <p>AIOU uses a unique grading system: 20% assignments, 30% workshops/quiz, and 50% final exams. Passing requires 50% marks.</p> <p>AU's evaluation is solely based on passing marks in the final examination.</p>
Course Coordinator Responsibilities	<p>Course coordinators at AIOU oversee the smooth running of each class during delivering the lesson according to the synchronous workshops. The course uploaded presentation during the live coordinator uses WhatsApp for sessions. They lack the ability to activate communication with the resource audio or camera for students during the persons teaching the same course during sessions or provide any relevant resource the live sessions.</p>
Issue Resolution	<p>AIOU's coordinators report technical issues to the ICT team via WhatsApp. A special WhatsApp group is used for live sessions either experienced by the coordination and monitoring.</p> <p>AU has a dedicated moderator who handles the technological issues during live sessions either experienced by the coordinators or students.</p>

This comparison examines the unique characteristics of online classes at Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) and Anadolu University (AU) including their scheduling, course coordination, learning management systems, evaluation standards, and problem-solving procedures. Each institution employs distinct strategies customized to its instructional methodology and technology frameworks.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of the study was to find out the perspective of academicians at Allama Iqbal Open University and Anadolu University regarding technological noise they face while teaching online courses.

Research Questions

1. How is the teaching-learning process in online courses impacted by technological noise at AIOU and Anadolu University?
2. How do AIOU and Anadolu University manage technological noise in their online courses?
3. How do cultural variations affect the experience of technical noise in online courses at AIOU and Anadolu University?

This study provides the opportunity of cross-cultural examination of impact that technological noise has on teaching-learning process through comparative analysis of technology usage in online courses at Allama Iqbal Open University and Anadolu University. There are no smooth progresses when it comes to advancements in e-learning as this is a domain within which technology dominates

Literature Review

Distance learning has revolutionized education by making it accessible as never before. At the same time, it has imposed a series of technological problems for both teachers and learners that tend to disrupt learning at times. In spite of their differences in culture, AIOU and AU have in common a battle with technological interference in distance education. Disturbances such as abrupt cut-offs, system failures, and connectivity issues may prove difficult for students to follow and adjust to online classrooms. Not only do these interruptions disrupt communication, but they also weaken student engagement, consequently influencing the general quality of education. In view of the above challenges, both universities underscore the significance of eliminating technological noise to develop more interactive and engaging online lessons. Research identifies some major obstacles, including limited digital access, poor institutional support, digital literacy gaps, and unreliable technology infrastructure. This literature review examines these pertinent issues, reviewing the current research and suggesting ways to improve the online learning experience.

Digital inequality is one of the major obstacles identified. It affects the availability of technology and the internet. Iqbal, Toor, and Fatima (2023) also examined the technical issues faced by students and teachers at women's universities in Lahore amid the COVID-19 pandemic. According to their findings, an overwhelming majority of students had deficits in accessing reliable technology, which significantly affected their ability to participate in online learning. Similarly, Deng and Sun (2022) identified the different e-learning challenges faced by disadvantaged minority-serving institution students, including technical, cultural, and financial problems. These findings emphasize the significance of addressing digital accessibility to enhance the efficacy of online learning.

The shift towards online learning has also highlighted institutional support disparities. Alivo, Cerbito, and Formaran (2022) have identified the self-reports of challenges faced with the abrupt change from asynchronous and synchronous online learning faced by radiologic technology students. Their findings indicated institutional support shortcomings and technological problems having greater impacts on students' academic performance than digital literacy problems. Akhter et al. (2022) further discovered institutionally supported deficiencies strengthened students' reluctance to initiate online learning, especially among developing nations such as Bangladesh.

Another concern largely discussed in academic literature is the deficiency of digital literacy and professional growth among instructors. Verma et al. (2023) explored barriers to adopting Education 5.0 and found that constraints related to technological advances, having a heavy workload, and insufficient self-efficacy of the teacher were top constraints that made the academicians unable to efficiently utilize technology as a pedagogy tool for teaching. The Kumar et al. (2022) study confirmed this fact, indicating that both technological and behavioral constraints were key factors in the engagement of students on online learning platforms, with teachers struggling to adjust to digital platforms.

The issue of technological infrastructure and connectivity remains a central in online learning studies. Nichuhovska et al. (2024) also examined the accessibility issues of the online learning environment and identified technological backlogs, inadequate material resources, and poor network connectivity as key obstacles. Yeh and Tsai (2022) also highlighted that technology-related obstacles, such as unreliable internet connectivity and over-reliance on digital content, were to blame for decreasing student engagement and causing video conferencing related fatigue.

Among the determinants of concern is how technical barriers affect learning outcomes. Demir Kaymak and Horzum (2022) looked at the determinants of academic performance in online learning environments and established that administrative concerns, technical difficulties, and poor motivation on the part of the learner were among the determinants of learners' perceived learning outcomes. In addition, Sumalinog (2022) provided a more detailed explanation of the issues confronting teachers in online-only settings, noting that technological, attitudinal, and environmental limitations all served to negate efforts at sustaining learner engagement and enhancing teaching effectiveness.

To overcome these, different research studies offer solutions to enhance online learning. For example, Kumar et al. (2022) suggest more technical support and faculty development to tackle digital illiteracy issues.

Akhter et al. (2022) suggest strengthening institutional support systems to better cater to the learning requirement of students. In addition, Yeh and Tsai (2022) recommend creating more inclusive digital learning spaces to minimize the effect of connectivity problems on student engagement. At a larger level, the literature depicts the diversified landscape of technological challenges in distance learning requiring sweeping measures for managing digital disparities, institutional support, capacity building, and infrastructural considerations. Applying the recommendations given can assist institutions of higher learning in creating more inclusive and effective online learning environments to serve the learners and the teachers themselves during the age of the digital society.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design centered on the academicians from both universities having experience of online teaching.

Target Population

Academicians teaching online courses at undergraduate level at Allama Iqbal Open University, Pakistan and Anadolu University, Turkiye constituted the population of the study.

Participant selection

The academicians/moderators who were conducting online classes were selected as respondents. In view of the unique working of online classes at Anadolu University the moderators responsible for the technical aspects of online session were included in the study along with the academicians conducting the online sessions. In all, 5 academicians from AIOU; 5 academicians and 5 moderators from AU were interviewed.

Research tool

The instrument of the study was an interview protocol having semi-structured questions where respondents shared their views about causes of technological noise, its impact upon the teaching learning process as well as the means of management generally adopted by them. Further they also gave context specific recommendations for reducing the technological noise during online sessions at each institution. The interviews were conducted face to face with the informed audio recording consent of the participants.

Findings of Interviews at AIOU and AU

The analysis of interviews with academicians at AIOU, academicians and moderators at Anadolu University (AU) provides a comprehensive understanding of the various ways technological noise disrupts online learning.

The main themes identify challenges from multiple sources were:

Hardware AIOU

Hardware problems often interrupt Allama Iqbal Open University online courses, both for students and academicians. Slow or outdated computers and low-memory systems freeze the screen, crash software, and slow down course material loading. Academicians tend to fix technical issues, which increases their workload. As one academician mentioned,

"Occasionally, I must diagnose and correct problems in a system. For instance, on an occasion, the microphone was not responding to the unmute command, necessitating adjustments to the microphone settings. Likewise, there are situations when the desktop computer does not work appropriately."

Students also experience problems such as low sound volume and display issues with PowerPoint slides, usually having to relog. Another academician said,

"Students often complain about the lack or low level of the academician's voice, as well as sporadic problems with the clarity of PowerPoint presentations. In this situation, I recommend that they log in again. Sometimes I ask them about their mobile or laptop devices, as older models tend to have poor internet functionalities."

Low-quality audio from malfunctioning microphones or speakers also impacts understanding, rendering lessons more difficult to follow. Where there is poor access to modern equipment, students use old devices, which makes it difficult to participate in online learning.

A faculty member suggested,

"As we are engaged in online teaching and learning, it would be advisable to furnish the faculty with the necessary equipment. The university can implement a program to provide instalment facilities for resource persons to purchase laptops and other equipment."

Second, slow or unreliable internet connectivity restricts students from downloading resources or maintaining connection. Closing these technological loopholes will be vital to an improved and accessible online learning experience.

Hardware AU

Interviews with Anadolu University (AU) demonstrate that hardware-based technical noise presents great challenges for virtual classrooms. Sound quality emerges as the major concern since distorted sound from added microphones impacts online lectures and discussions. An academician stated,

"My microphone would record paper ruffling sounds when I'm reading notes in class. If I set the papers aside, it produces ruffling sounds which could interfere or disturb students listening to the lectures."

Another noted, *"My laptop used to get heated up, and the fan made a lot of noise that the microphone caught. This disturbed the lecture, and I got messages from the students that they were having difficulty following the lecture."*

These incidents stress the importance of quality audio gear to ensure easy communication.

Ensuring a stable audio connection is a priority in online classes, as lectures can continue without video but not without sound. The use of outdated devices further contributes to technological noise, leading to compatibility issues, slower processing speeds, and barriers to adopting new digital tools. Although ideal conditions allow seamless functionality, connectivity issues remain a major concern.

A participant observed, *"Everything works smoothly in those cases. Also, problems may occur due to the servers for a very short period. If the internet connection, internet infrastructure is good, the technology hardware is good, then we do not face any serious problems."*

The findings emphasize the importance of upgrading hardware, maintaining reliable connectivity, and adopting proactive measures to enhance the overall virtual learning experience at AU.

Software AIOU

Software and connectivity issues significantly disrupt online courses at AIOU, leading to sluggish performance, unresponsive functionalities, and browser crashes. Compatibility problems between outdated software and e-learning systems cause security risks, while poor update management introduces new errors that disrupt network stability. Some sound configuration issues, such as incompatible microphones, further hinder communication. An academician shared,

"Occasionally, students contact me as a group to inform me that they are unable to hear my voice. In response, I clarify that the problem lies not with me, but with them. If at least one student in the class can hear my voice, it indicates that the connection from my end is strong. Therefore, the ICT team recommend that the students may login through a compatible browser."

Malfunctioning software also delays assignments, causes technical glitches in presentations, and disrupts instruction. The broader online learning environment at AIOU relies on an intricate ecosystem of hardware and software, where any failure can disrupt class continuity. To address accessibility issues, a faculty member suggested,

"Every online course we offer should be made accessible as a digital package for students to purchase. I have observed an Indian model that included a compact enclosure like the external hard discs you are familiar with. The compact container included a little device resembling a hard drive, which stored an entire course curriculum comprising audio, video, and text materials. The students can acquire it through a custom order."

Student behavior in online classes also presents challenges, with distractions impacting engagement. Another academician indicated,

"We instruct, but we do not know how much they understand. A chat box tool is available that allows students to communicate. One of the challenges, though, is that a lot of the time, they talk with other students rather than listening to the instructor."

In addition, constant connectivity problems, bandwidth constraints, and inadequate internet infrastructure hinder students from accessing course content and engaging effectively, ultimately compromising the online learning process.

Software AU

A study of software-related disruptions at Anadolu University (AU) identifies major issues impacting online sessions. A significant issue is non-responsive PowerPoint presentations, which lower participation and cause frustration among participants. According to a participant,

"Sometimes the resource person can't open the camera or cannot shift the slides."

Moreover, slow or lagged chat messages create communication setbacks, disrupting lesson flows. Issues like freezing and images with a warped appearance from screens also hamper virtual lessons and affect understanding. As related by an academician,

"Sometimes I receive feedback from students that I cannot hear your voice, your video is stuck like the screen is frozen."

Another is the browser compatibility challenge because other browsers beyond Chrome might hinder connectivity, rendering online platforms inaccessible. According to one of the participants,

"The compatibility between the software and the browser in use may cause disruption like Chrome or Safari. They might use a different type of browser, not Explorer, but Chrome be suggested. So based on the students' browser, based on students' internet connections, based on the internet connection at my home, I have had problems."

Addressing these software disruptions requires technical improvements and a collective effort to standardize browser usage and enhance software functionality, ensuring a seamless online learning experience for both academicians and students at AU.

Online Environment AIOU

Technological interference significantly impacts the quality of instruction and overall online learning experience at Allama Iqbal Open University. Issues with microphones, speakers, and search engine software disrupt class continuity, affecting both students and academicians. A participant suggested,

"Every online course we offer should be made accessible as a digital package for students to purchase... a compact container included a little device resembling a hard drive, which stored an entire course curriculum comprising audio, video, and text materials."

Student behavior also plays a role in technological disruptions.

"We provide guidance, but we are uncertain about their level of comprehension. There is a chat box function available for students to communicate. However, a major concern is that students often engage in conversations with each other instead of paying attention to the teacher," noted an academician.

Disruptions from non-academic activities affect both student focus and academician effectiveness. Additionally, poor internet connectivity, bandwidth limitations, and frequent interruptions hinder students from accessing course materials, participating in discussions, and engaging with the class, further obstructing a conducive learning environment.

Online Environment AU

The online learning environment at Anadolu University (AU) presents various technological challenges that disrupt virtual interactions. A major issue is auditory communication, with unpredictable sound behavior, background noise, and microphone malfunctions affecting engagement. One of the participants noted,

"Sometimes the academicians don't know that the mic is not working and how to unmute it. So, the technical team (moderator) has to do the adjustment at the back end."

Another added, *"We cannot hear you, or the voice comes and goes. There is noise in the background."*

The reliance on chat as the primary engagement tool further hampers real-time discussion, slowing down feedback and limiting spontaneous interaction. Additionally, academicians struggle with an overwhelming flow of messages, making it difficult to address student inquiries effectively.

Platform limitations also restrict engagement, as faculty members can only upload PowerPoint presentations, preventing them from integrating diverse materials or responding promptly to student messages. An academician explained,

"We can't upload anything, just PowerPoint, but sometimes I use surveys for questions on ekampus. Due to the large inflow of messages, we can't facilitate all the students by replying to their messages in sequence along with delivering the lecture."

In disciplines like social sciences, faculty stress the need for flexibility beyond textbooks. Another participant shared,

"Especially for social sciences, we as academicians cannot be restricted to the textbook... I want to unpack a certain concept, but I have to limit myself to the content in the textbook."

These challenges—ranging from audio disruptions and communication barriers to content restrictions—highlight the need for improvements in technical infrastructure, training, and platform flexibility to enhance the online learning experience at AU.

Network Connectivity AIOU

Inadequate internet connections cause buffering, freezing, and slow downloads, delaying or disrupting classes. Poor bandwidth affects audio and video quality, making comprehension difficult, especially when visual materials require elaboration. An academician noted,

"The fundamental inquiry regarding our nation, our culture, our city revolves around the internet, which is the most fundamental concern. Individuals residing in areas with internet access, whether in rural or urban settings, see a 60% reduction in difficulties compared to those without such access."

However, those without stable internet often face frequent disconnections and long delays before rejoining classes, sometimes waiting 20-30 minutes to reconnect. Additionally, students in areas with computers still struggle due to electricity failures and load shedding. Another faculty member highlighted,

"Adapting to new technical advancements was not a problem as we were familiar with the procedures, but the challenge lies in having a reliable internet connection. Therefore, this is a bilateral procedure."

Recurrent connectivity issues prevent students from accessing crucial course segments, reducing their understanding of the subject matter. Limited high-speed internet in rural and remote areas worsens these difficulties, creating significant barriers to effective online learning and increasing frustration among students.

Network Connectivity AU

Network connectivity issues at Anadolu University (AU) significantly impact virtual classes, with sluggish internet, automatic logouts, and weak signals disrupting online lessons. Poor connectivity, especially during peak evening hours, affects engagement and smooth lesson delivery. A participant noted,

"The first and foremost problem is the internet connection. If the internet connection is weak, no matter how good hardware you have, you will face disruptions during the lecture."

Despite strong office connections, faculty members reported that Wi-Fi is often weaker than home networks, leading to reliance on cable connections, which are inconvenient.

"There are always studios available to us for the conduction of lessons, but for that, we need to go to the services building. The issue is that the Wi-Fi connection in my office is worse than the internet connection in my home. To resolve the issue, I can always connect with the cable, but it's not very convenient."

Automatic logouts further disrupt classes, often requiring browser cache clearance or moderator assistance. An academician recounted,

"Just once I accidentally left the lecture and mistakenly logged out of the e-kampus system as I was trying to resolve a problem with my microphone... I refreshed the system, and it logged me out. I couldn't log in again because it showed that the session had been completed."

The inability of faculty members to re-login independently forces them to rely on moderators, wasting valuable class time and causing frustration. *"That is because you don't have any option of re-logging into your class by yourself."*

While major disconnections are rare and sessions can be rescheduled, this affects student motivation and disrupts the learning process.

"In terms of internet disconnections, we rarely face such problems as we have a strong internet connection in the offices. In case it happens, we can postpone the class, but it affects the motivation level of students."

These challenges highlight the need for technical improvements in the e-kampus system, better support mechanisms for educators, and stronger internet infrastructure to ensure instructional consistency and a seamless online learning experience at AU.

Learning Management System (LMS) AIOU

The Learning Management System (LMS) is not without glitches, often causing login issues that waste class time and disrupt learning. An academician noted,

"The primary concern was the utilisation of a system which was most facilitating, so the university switched from Big Blue Button to Microsoft Teams. As a result, numerous confusions and concerns arose. Presently the sessions are being conducted on Microsoft Teams via LMS and are attended by students from across the country. The issue is that if they access Microsoft Teams directly, their presence in class is not recorded on LMS as Microsoft Teams is another platform. Utilising the login to LMS (aaghi.aiou.edu.pk) simplifies this process by eliminating attendance concerns. However, students and resource persons who have directly joined Microsoft Teams have attendance complications. This has not just affected the students but also the resource persons by hindering their billing process."

Navigation challenges within the LMS further impede student engagement by making it difficult to locate learning materials. A faculty member suggested,

"Training sessions, such as instructional videos related to navigation within the employed LMS should be made available on the interface of the Learning Management System (LMS) to facilitate students and resource persons."

Learning Management System (LMS) AU

Interview data highlights significant technical challenges in Anadolu University's Learning Management System (LMS), particularly regarding group size restrictions and system efficiency. A key issue is the limitation that only 300 students can join a live session on Big Blue Button, though this number fluctuates between 200 and 400 based on login demand. A participant noted,

"Another restriction is that the limit of participants in a live session on Big Blue Button is 300. Sometimes there had been confusions, it is 200 or 400 but currently it is 300 depending on the login load during the live session."

This constraint results in overcrowded classrooms, limiting student engagement and making it difficult for academicians to manage discussions. The technical infrastructure struggles with scalability, preventing seamless access for all students.

Additional issues include weak video conferencing features and system vulnerabilities under high participant loads. An academician observed,

"Not all the students enrolled in a course can enter the system. They have this problem because we have a limit of 300 or sometimes 200 participants. This is the limitation of the Big Blue Button and the server."

Another noted, *"If there are a high number of participants, then some misconnections can occur in the form of video and voice disruptions."*

The use of mobile devices for online learning further complicates engagement due to limited interface functionality and inconsistent mobile internet connectivity.

"Sometimes mobile internet services do not work very well," remarked one respondent.

These limitations highlight the need for a more adaptable and technologically advanced LMS infrastructure to support the evolving demands of online education at AU.

User-end issues and non-educational technology AIOU

Audio transmission issues, technical distractions, and inadequate digital skills hinder participation in online classes. Unnecessary messages, outdated tools, and lack of troubleshooting expertise reduce engagement and disrupt the learning process. Students often struggle with login difficulties, poor audio transmission, and unstable internet connections, as a participant noted,

"Students frequently express dissatisfaction with their inability to join the class, login successfully, and, even if they manage to participate, they complain about the lack of audible voice transmission."

Additionally, non-instructional technology, such as social media and mobile notifications, further diverts attention, amplifying technological interference and negatively impacting the teaching-learning process.

User-end issues and non-educational technology AU

Analyzing user-related problems and non-educational technology in online classrooms reveals several key challenges. Outdated equipment, such as modems, complicates virtual learning. A participant noted,

"It was an old modem. I had problems because of that. Sometimes the students have problems due to the limitations of the device they are using."

Dependence on moderators for reconnection adds another hurdle, causing delays and missed lessons.

"I asked the moderator if there's something wrong with the system on my end, the moderator said no everything is fine. There must be some problem at the students' end."

The reliance on moderators and inefficient troubleshooting processes highlights the need for clearer communication and streamlined technical support.

Limited technological proficiency among users further complicates online learning. A lack of experience leads to confusion and delays, underscoring the need for better training. One example described an academician struggling with a non-working camera:

"Once an academician reported that the camera is not working, and the screen is black. I made all the essential checks at the backend and found no issue. The problem persisted, so I had to walk the academician through step by step and while doing that I realized that the camera shutter on the device is not open."

Such user-end issues often disrupt classes, reinforcing the importance of digital literacy. Another participant pointed out,

"Maybe it was due to the students' internet connection, or they do not have the expertise to deal with modern technology."

These challenges highlight the need for improved internet access, efficient communication channels, reduced reliance on moderators, and comprehensive user training to enhance the online learning experience.

Table 2: Themes wise cultural variations in technological noise in online courses at AIOU and Anadolu University

Construct	AIOU Themes	AU Themes
1. Hardware	Obsolete or inadequate gadgets, malfunctioning computers, outdated devices like mobile phones, tablets, or desktops.	Distortion from external microphones, modem signals outreach obstacles, utilization of unreliable devices by students.
2. Software	Compatibility problems, outdated software, audio glitches, difficulties in uploading assignments.	PowerPoint irresponsiveness, delayed/failing chat delivery, video freezing, issues with browsers other than Chrome.
3. Disturbances	Disruptions caused by students, problems with the Internet connection.	Speech interruptions, background sounds, microphone malfunctions, automatic muting, overwhelmed chat box with messages.
4. Network Connectivity	Lack of network connection, interruptions, buffering, areas with little access to speed digital services.	Slow internet speed, automatic disconnections, absence of re-logging without moderator intervention.

Construct	AIOU Themes	AU Themes
5. Learning Management System (LMS)	Technical errors, navigation difficulties, login problems.	Login restrictions, maximum limit of 300 participants, Big Blue Button issues, teaching from mobile devices problematic.
6. User-End Issue and Non-Educational Technology	Various difficulties include inadequate internet connectivity, hearing issues, disruptive messages, and lack of computer literacy among academicians and students.	Exclusive dependence on chat, reliance on moderators for reconnection, disparities in computer literacy among academicians and students.

The construct wise difference in the themes of technological noise reveals cultural variations between the context of each institution. The comparison highlights the complex obstacles encountered by Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) and Anadolu University (AU) in the field of online education, uncovering both shared and distinct elements within the context of each institution.

Conclusion

- Technological noise at AIOU presents significant barriers to effective online learning. Outdated student devices, malfunctioning academician computers, software compatibility issues, and audio-video glitches disrupt instructional delivery and interaction. Slow internet access, repeated buffering, and restricted availability of high-speed services, especially in rural locales, add to learning limitations. Technical issues related to LMS, navigation problems, and login details also cause disruptions in seamless engagement. Lack of proper technical competencies and mobile notifications distract students, thus impacting real-time interactions. Resolution of these issues through infrastructural upgrades, augmenting digital competencies training, and robust support structures is imperative to the creation of a smooth, efficient online learning experience.
- Technological interference is still a major issue in Anadolu University (AU) online learning. Malfunctions in hardware, unreliable internet connectivity, and software incompatibility still interrupt virtual classrooms, even as AU works to ensure hardware efficiency, guarantee stable connectivity, and optimize the Learning Management System (LMS). User-related challenges, including the requirement for increased technical proficiency among academicians and students, also add to technological noise. Mitigating these issues by enhancing infrastructure, increasing digital literacy training, and providing proactive technical support is necessary to build a better and smoother online learning process.

Discussion

The results of this research are consistent with previous studies on the effects of technological noise in distance learning, stressing its negative impact on students and academicians. The comparative study between Allama Iqbal Open University (AIOU) and Anadolu University (AU) points out major differences in how each university feels and copes with technological issues. The study results reveal that AU has a more organized and effective method of countering technological disruptions, while AIOU is plagued with ongoing hardware, software, connectivity, and Learning Management System (LMS) inefficiencies issues.

One of the most significant issues addressed in the study is digital inequality, which Iqbal, Toor, and Fatima (2023) also mentioned as a contributing factor, and they discovered that students in disadvantaged institutions have trouble with access to reliable technology. Likewise, Deng and Sun (2022) emphasized financial and technical constraints to effective online learning participation. The present research echoes such apprehensions, especially in the case of AIOU, where students and academicians often face old equipment and a lack of high-speed internet access, further complicating technological noise.

Institutional support has been recognized as another vital aspect in guaranteeing the efficacy of online learning. The Alivo, Cerbito, and Formaran (2022) study showed that poor institutional support exacerbated the issues of online learning. The same findings from AIOU affirm this, as restricted technical support and ineffective troubleshooting measures further demote the online learning process. AU, however, is favored with a more organized support system that reduces disruptions.

Student and academician digital literacy is yet another factor that plays a part in technological noise. Verma et al. (2023) and Kumar et al. (2022) identified that insufficient training and uncertainty about handling digital tools discourage teachers from making the most of online learning platforms. The academicians and students at AIOU also share similar problems, grappling with solving routine software-related issues, navigating LMS navigation-related problems, and resolving user-end technical issues. By comparison, AU's system is more organized to minimize reliance on external technical assistance and allow for more seamless online experiences.

Connectivity problems continue to be an ongoing issue, as mentioned in earlier research by Nichuhovska et al. (2024) and Yeh and Tsai (2022), who found unreliable internet connectivity as a major impediment to student participation. The current research substantiates that AIOU students and academicians are often plagued by connectivity problems, such as sluggish speeds and regular disconnections, which interrupt continuity of classes. AU, though also suffering from connectivity problems, has a more robust infrastructure, reducing the effect of such issues.

The effect of technology noise on learning engagement and academic performance is clear in the study of Demir Kaymak and Horzum (2022), which recognized administrative issues and technical interruptions as central determinants of learning outcomes. The issues of AIOU, including software breakdowns, non-responsive LMS functions, and login issues, have a considerable impact on student participation and academician effectiveness. AU's systematic approach and better digital infrastructure ensure a smoother learning environment.

These problems need to be addressed through targeted interventions. Kumar et al. (2022) recommend improved technical assistance and training for the faculty in order to avoid digital literacy issues. Akhter et al. (2022) also stress the importance of strong institutional support systems. These recommendations are validated through the findings of this research, especially in the context of AIOU, where technical infrastructure, digital training, and pro-active fault remediation measures could go a long way in cutting down technological noise. In addition, Yeh and Tsai (2022) suggest creating more inclusive virtual learning environments, which would be beneficial to both institutions in the process of developing their online education models.

The issue of technological noise in AIOU and AU calls for sustained investment in digital infrastructure, user education, and institutional assistance to achieve a high-quality online learning environment. Though AU showcases superior management of technological noise, AIOU has to undertake strategic changes to strengthen its online learning environment and reduce the digital education gap.

Recommendations

- In order to counter technological noise and improve online learning at AIOU, there should be a specialized technical support team with requisite skills to hold workshops and leave proper documentation regarding hardware and software troubleshooting. Upgrading network infrastructure is essential with coordination with Internet Service Providers (ISPs) to enhance connectivity, especially for students from remote areas. Moreover, the Learning Management System (LMS) must be optimized by creating a task force to evaluate enhancements, maintaining compatibility with devices, and conducting frequent training for users. Access to contemporary equipment must also be enhanced through collaborations with hardware vendors, providing instalment plans and financial incentives to students and faculty. Digital literacy courses need to be initiated in conjunction with educational technology experts, hosting teaching materials on the LMS and virtual workshops. Ongoing software management is required, with a specific team in charge of timely updates, system audits, and quick issue resolution. Backup software solutions need to be identified and implemented, with clear

guidelines and training sessions. In addition, low-cost student internet plans need to be formulated in consultation with ISPs, and awareness about choices and the enrolment process needs to be promoted. The development of inclusive digital study materials, like interactive course packs, will boost accessibility and motivation. Special digital skill courses and ongoing feedback loops need to be implemented through questionnaires and discussion forums to monitor challenges and initiate improvements.

- At Anadolu University (AU), technological noise are met by enhancing the hardware infrastructure to handle large-scale online learning, and precise instructions on microphone configuration to avoid sound distortions. The use of software should be maximized by standardizing compatible web browsers, frequent updates, and providing real-time technical support. The LMS can be upgraded by investigating alternative platforms with larger participant capacity and enhanced functionality, with compatibility across devices. Students and academicians must be given comprehensive training to increase digital literacy, with specific suggestions for enhancing internet signal strength and having a specialized technical support team. Technological expertise needs to be enhanced by providing accessible learning materials, minimizing dependency on moderators for resolving issues. A strategic plan for live sessions must be implemented, focusing on high-demand courses, restricting simultaneous logins, and optimizing system performance. Several sessions must be held for popular courses to allow for large enrollment without detracting from the engagement. Workshops for academicians should be held to improve computer proficiency and virtual instruction techniques. A sophisticated method for live sessions should be utilized, limiting participants per course to optimize learning outcomes and increase session dependability. Finally, ongoing monitoring and evaluation should be instituted through periodic monitoring of system performance, gathering feedback, and continuous communication with moderators to address new technical challenges that arise.

The adoption of these recommendations will allow AIOU and AU to considerably enhance their virtual learning environment, eliminate technological noise, and provide a more efficient and inclusive virtual learning experience for all concerned.

References

- Akhter, H., Abdul Rahman, A. A., Jafrin, N., Mohammad Saif, A. N., Esha, B. H., & Mostafa, R. (2022). Investigating the barriers that intensify undergraduates' unwillingness to online learning during COVID-19: A study on public universities in a developing country. *Cogent Education*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2022.2028342> .
- Alivo, R. A., Cerbito, A. F., & Formaran, M. J. A. (2022). Perceived Barriers in the Sudden Transition to Asynchronous and Synchronous Online Distance Learning of Radiologic Technology Student. *Online Submission*, 4(1), 74-81. <https://doi.org/10.54476/iimrj10>
- Deng, X., & Sun, R. (2022). Barriers to e-learning during crisis: A capital theory perspective on academic adversity. *Journal of Information Systems Education*, 33(1), 75-86. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/jise/vol33/iss1/9>
- Iqbal, N., Toor, S. I., & Fatima, T. (2023). Technological Barriers Towards Online Teaching During Covid-19 Pandemic: A Study of Women Universities of Lahore. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 5(01), 238-247. <https://doi.org/10.52567/pjsr.v5i01.997>
- Kaymak, Z. D., & Horzum, M. B. (2022). Student barriers to online learning as predictors of perceived learning and academic achievement. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 23(2), 97-106. <https://doi.org/10.17718/tojde.1096250>
- Kumar, P., Garg, R. K., Kumar, P., & Panwar, M. (2022). Teachers' perceptions of student barriers to sustainable engagement in online education. *International Journal of Knowledge and Learning*, 15(4), 373-408. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJKL.2022.126273>
- Nichuhovska, L., Nikolenko, L., Bondarenko, Z., Motorina, V., & Prykhodko, T. (2023). Challenges and prospects of online education in the context of barrier-free access. *Multidisciplinary Reviews*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.31893/multirev.2023spe020>
- Sumalinog, G. G. (2022). Barriers of online education in the new normal: Teachers' perspectives. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(1), 33-50. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.21.1.3>
- Verma, P., Arora, N., Ahmed, E., & Agarwal, V. (2023). Routing towards Education 5.0 via sustainable technology empowerment: Potential challenges to academicians in universities. *Journal of Statistics and Management Systems*, 26(7), 1759-1775. <https://doi.org/10.47974/JSMS-1144>
- Yeh, C. Y., & Tsai, C. C. (2022). Massive distance education: barriers and challenges in shifting to a complete online learning environment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 928717. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.928717>